

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #10

Gender inclusion in work processes with renewable energy projects in cities

By WiTEC

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Executive Summary

Figure 10.1. Gender inclusion in work processes with renewable energy projects in cities - Graphical Abstract

This study analyses two organizational change initiatives, one successful and one unsuccessful, to understand the factors influencing resistance and success in gender inclusion, figure 10.1. The purpose is to identify key elements for increasing the likelihood of success in similar projects.

Success factors include internal initiation, voluntary participation, theory-practice integration, expertise, adequate time for research and change, bridging status gaps, forming alliances, adopting an evolutionary approach, addressing resistance, and emphasizing fairness and justice.

Abstract

This study compares two different case studies on organisational change initiatives, one of which was deemed successful and the other one deemed unsuccessful; this study examines the reasons for the varying levels of resistance within these two projects with the purpose of identifying factors that can increase chances of success in similar initiatives. Success factors identified in this case study for change initiatives include internal initiation, voluntary participation, integration of

theory and practice, adequate expertise, allowing sufficient time for research and change, bridging status gaps, forming alliances with committed collaborators, adopting an evolutionary approach, addressing resistance, and emphasizing fairness and justice. These factors serve as guidelines for implementing effective change initiatives in organisations and are applied on the project RES4CITY in a shorter analysis.

Introduction

Within the area of organisational change, the term resistance to change is well-documented. Resistance to change is argued to be a main reason for failures in change initiatives, as it tends to introduce unanticipated delays to the process, aiming to keep the current situation (Pardo del Val & Martínez Fuentes, 2003).

Current research on resistance to change understands it as a systemic concept, as opposed to older sources – such as managerial literature – which oftentimes viewed the phenomenon as caused by individual psychological factors; another difference between older and newer perspectives on resistance is the view on whether it should be seen as a resource or as a threat – trying to fight it has grown outdated, as understanding it as a form of feedback instead becomes more popular (Blomqvist & Frennberg, 2012).

It is suggested that gender equality action programs that challenge gender order is bound to be met by resistance, judging by literature in the field. This case study is based on an article examining the differences between two different feminist action research projects: (i) the successful FGF project which was not met by resistance and (ii) the not very successful BAF project, which was met by resistance (Blomqvist & Frennberg, 2012; Meyerson &

Kolb, 2009). The objective of this work is to extract the relevant lessons from these examples, in order to create better understanding and conditions for making relevant action initiatives work within the context of the RES4CITY project.

Description of Case Study

In this section, two different feminist action research projects will be presented; all descriptions of the FGF project are from Blomqvist and Frennberg's report (2012), and all descriptions of the BAF project are from either Blomqvist and Frennberg's or Meyerson and Kolb's report (2009).

In this case study, it is advised to reflect on the reasons why two similar projects might either fail or succeed. It is recommended to think about reasons for and forms of initiatives within the two projects, structural conditions within their organisations, as well as general factors that might benefit or disadvantage gender equality interventions. The findings are presented in the case study solution, along with more detailed accounts of the differences that led to the varying end results. Worth considering is how this case study may have parallels to the RES4CITY project; consider different ways of viewing the structures of the project: (1) RES4CITY as an entity

consisting of its internal bodies, (2) RES4CITY as the entity with external partners and collaborators, and (3) RES4CITY with partners and people involved in the project's interventions (for example students involved with micro-credentials).

The FGF project

VINNOVA (the Swedish Governmental Agency for Innovation Systems) funded the FGF (Change and Gender in FOCUS) project in 2008, which aimed to enhance organisational competitiveness and sustainable growth within an organisation, following the logic that these goals would be achieved as gender equality increases – the program therefore focused on the gender aspect, for instance by increasing awareness and knowledge of gender-related mindsets as well as creativity restricting actions within organisations. Expected outcomes included enhanced organisational competence, integration of

new gender perspectives, attracting more female researchers, and developing new application areas and research projects in the civilian sector.

The organisation's Information Systems Division initiated and organised the planning and launch of the FGF project. Following the decision to apply for funding, a gender researcher and a consultant were added to the project team. The project was set up with a group of core employees who were selected based on their interest and commitment; these, so-called, co-researchers came from different parts of the organisation and had varying levels of experience. During selection of co-researchers, the project aimed to include people who could facilitate dialogue and internal communication, including management staff, department managers, business managers, and those working with the official gender equality plan; gender ratio of co-researchers was approximately equal. The co-researchers received training on the

theoretical aspects of gender in an organisational context and were involved in defining and implementing project tasks.

The work plan of the project was divided into three main areas: organisational culture, internal processes, and dissemination; these areas were studied to examine gender and equality-related processes and practices within the organisation and to take actions for change.

The organisational culture area was studied through seminars, suggested literature and discussions conducted by the project team and the gender researcher from Uppsala University. The co-researchers observed their environment and discussed their observations within the project team, which helped increase knowledge on gender issues and gender theory among the team and other managers and employees. Later, this knowledge was used to work

on creating a more creative research environment and improving career opportunities by scrutinising factors that influence career prospects and making career paths more transparent. Metrics were collected to visualise the ratios of female and male employees in different areas, and these were used to discuss the present state, underlying causes, and suggestions to change the situation. Metrics played a significant role in internal processes, but the focus was on increasing knowledge and adapting procedures to facilitate change. The Information Systems division launched an extensive recruitment campaign early in the project, and the project team discussed how to attract female researchers through advertisement formulations. These discussions were then communicated to the department managers in the project team who presented them to the division management group during discussions. Changes were made in advertising and interviewing practices to prevent gender bias in

recruitment. As a result, the percentage of female employees increased from 11% to 13.5% over the course of the project.

The project identified project management as an important platform, as project managers have high visibility and are appreciated within the organisation and by customers. However, metrics showed that female researchers were underrepresented, especially among project managers leading large projects. To address this, it was made mandatory for all larger projects to have an assistant project manager, which would allow more employees to develop the skills needed for project management. Additionally, the wage structure was surveyed, and the project team gave input to the gender equality plan, making the plan more comprehensive and explicitly outlining its goals. The project team also emphasized the importance of allowing the knowledge and results

acquired during the project to influence the equality plan for a long-term implementation of the results.

Internal and external communication is an essential aspect of any research project; the project team regularly disseminated their results in seminars for management and all employees, and the co-researchers presented the project at department meetings on a regular basis.

The BAF project

The FGF project will be compared to a similar but relatively unsuccessful action research project, referred to as the BAF (Beyond Armchair Feminism) project, in which feminist researchers aimed to create a gender-equal workplace at a large global retail and manufacturing company.

The theory behind the BAF project centred around the idea that gender inequities in organisations stem from ingrained assumptions, values,

and practices that grant power and privilege to specific groups of men at the expense of women and other men – from this perspective, the researchers aimed to establish transformative change that fundamentally alter these mentioned power relations. In the project’s grant proposal, a “gender lens” was outlined, consisting of four sets of questions to probe the underlying assumptions and practices that sustain gender inequities: (1) questions exploring the deeply entrenched assumptions and values that support hierarchical, competitive, and controlling organisational structures, (2) questions regarding the valuation and devaluation of different work styles and activities, particularly in relation to gender, (3) questions exploring the relationship between the public sphere of work and the private sphere of home and family, and (4) questions delving into the ideology of individualism and competition within organisations.

The BAF project begun as one of the feminist researchers had connections to the founder and CEO of the company, and they both shared a vision of creating a gender-equal workplace; therefore, the project had a clear top-down initiation. During the feminist researchers’ initial visits to the organisation, they faced challenges in translating their theoretical framework into practical implementation as people struggled to grasp the broader understanding of gender beyond its association with women. The proposed process seemed ambiguous and lacked specific outcomes and timelines, leading to requests for concrete deliverables. The researchers relied on examples from other projects, but their applicability was not always clear to the BAF project.

To initiate the project, the authors needed to explain how applying a gender lens could be beneficial to the organisations; they emphasized a dual-agenda approach, highlighting how employing a gender lens to identify areas for intervention

could benefit both the business and promote gender equity. They shared success stories from other projects where interventions designed to enhance gender equity had led to significant business-related improvements. This resulted in people primarily perceiving the researchers as problem-solvers for business-related challenges; many executives volunteered to collaborate on projects that they believed would address pressing business issues within their own departments, and it remained unclear to what extent the group understood or prioritised the gender equity aspect of the researchers' agenda. The partners from the organisation chose one of their manufacturing plants as the starting point for the researchers' project; the plant operated in an outdated manner, with job and level segregation based on gender – women held lower-level positions while men occupied supervisory and management roles, however, morale was low among both genders with little hope for advancement.

The plant's physical and cultural isolation within the company made it an attractive choice, as it was rarely visited by headquarters and seen as a separate entity. Looking back, the researchers concluded they were directed to this plant because their impact there would be limited, reducing the potential for harm.

Case Study Solution

In this section, the cases will be compared to each other in order to extract the meaningful differences setting the two projects apart and leading to differing outcomes. According to Blomqvist and Frennberg (2012), the different outcomes had to do with the lack of resistance to the FGF project, outlined in the following themes; reflections by Meyerson and Kolb (2009) are used to complete the analysis of the outcomes:

- **Initiation**

The BAF project was started by external feminist researchers who entered the organisation and were friends with the CEO of the company, while the FGF project was initiated from within by the Information Systems Division with the involvement of a consultant and gender researcher. This form of internal initiation in the FGF project is crucial for legitimacy within a change project – which in the case study was observed to indeed be the case, by an external observer confirming the FGF project enjoyed a high degree of legitimacy at the workplace.

- **Voluntariness**

The BAF project had internal collaborators assigned by the CEO while the FGF project had a group of voluntary co-researchers, hand-picked based on their expected interest in the project. The FGF co-researchers were a diverse group of middle managers, researchers,

project managers, and administrators with a high educational level and as a group they were deemed stable; the stability of the group was due to their voluntary participation and commitment to the project's outcomes as they were interested in the issue. In contrast, the BAF project's collaboration was not entirely voluntary, as the collaborators were assigned by their superiors. Also, it might be argued that the BAF project's failure to communicate its theoretical frameworks in intelligible ways of practical implementation, might have led to less enthusiasm for the project within the organisation.

- **Epistemological conditions**

The BAF project faced difficulties in applying gender theory to practice, while the FGF project had an easier time due to the gender researcher providing talks and discussions on gender theory early on (Blomqvist & Frennberg, 2012). The BAF project had to consult a group of their armchair and practitioner feminist colleagues

to develop a framework and pedagogy for the organisation members to learn the basics of feminist theory for them to learn how to work with a gender lens as a basis for critique; from where they started, most organisation members had trouble understanding the meaning behind words such as gender (Meyerson & Kolb, 2009).

Most of the co-researchers in the FGF project were researchers themselves and were used to academic and scientific processes – such as reading scientific texts – which made it possible to integrate gender research articles into the project. The shared critical and problematising approach of both the natural sciences and gender research disciplines allowed for careful mapping of the organisation and the identification of points calling for change. Co-researchers functioned as gender researchers, making observations on gender practices and masculinity

performances in their workplace and identifying relevant points and processes for gendering the work organisation. (Blomqvist & Frennberg, 2012)

- **Time for research**

In the BAF project, internal collaborators kept asking for concrete outcomes and deliverables, but the researchers couldn't provide them. In contrast, the co-researchers in the FGF project, who were researchers themselves, understood the time-consuming nature of research and the lack of quick fixes. They took responsibility for identifying ongoing goals and targets for change and gave the change process the necessary time.

- **Equality**

Action research typically involves bridging the gap between the action researcher and the participants to achieve equality in their relationship. This often requires raising the status of participating

employees. However, in the FGF project, the gender researcher did not have to bridge any significant status gap; if there was a status gap, it did not favour the gender researcher – in this organisational setting, as in many other societal contexts, natural and technological sciences have a higher status compared to gender research.

In the BAF project, the researchers' goal from the outset was to identify a small group of collaborators who would share their commitment to making changes – they therefore sought to establish an alliance with a willing part of the organisation, with which to collaborate. This approach differs from how it was done in the FGF project.

However, it is important to have in mind that the organisations in the two projects were quite different, and thus may have provided different conditions for equal encounters between researchers and participants. In the BAF project, the researchers worked on a

manufacturing plant with old-fashioned operational structures characterized by sex-segregated hierarchies disadvantaging female workers – therefore the female researchers' involvement might have been met with resistance from the beginning, given the oppressive structures within the context. (Meyerson & Kolb, 2009)

- **Powering the core group**

Equal opportunity work is typically managed by employees who do not hold positions of power within an organisation. However, this was not the case in the FGF project. The core group consisted of two out of five department managers, one out of three business managers, and the divisional director was part of the project reference group. This means that the project had the support of individuals in powerful positions, which had an impact on the group's organisational skills, insights and impact. Many of the

change agents knew how to manage change and, importantly, what not to do in order to avoid any obstacles.

In the BAF project, the researchers felt that the internal collaborators that had been chosen were not ready to fully collaborate – they were reluctant to enter the proposed processes and had troubles understanding the project’s approach enough to responsibly sign on; however, they felt compelled to move forward with the researchers due to the commitment from the senior team, particularly the Chief Executive – in this way the BAF project had support from the top levels of the organisation, yet in practice this was lost due to the assigned collaborators not being ready to collaborate. (Meyerson & Kolb, 2009)

- **Not revolutionary**

Change that challenges the status quo can be difficult to

implement, especially if it involves gender relations. The changes proposed by the FGF project were not revolutionary, but rather evolutionary in nature. The project did not propose quotas, which could have been met with resistance in an organisation that valued meritocracy. However, the changes made were still significant, as they integrated a gender perspective into the policies, procedures, and practices of the organisation. The project targeted the entire organisation, and the perspective was long-term and continuous.

- **Not being too sensitive**

When change agents are implementing changes, they may interpret employee reactions as resistance. Looking back at the FGF project, the change agents realised that there were events that could have been classified as resistance had they been more sensitive or anxious about employee responses.

For example, there were delays in receiving salary data and in signing the gender equality plan, and employees raised questions about the link between gender equality and productivity during a seminar. However, the change agents did not view these incidents as resistance at the time and were glad they didn't, as the salary data was eventually delivered, and the equal opportunity plan was signed after thoughtful consideration. The questions raised at the seminar prompted the change agents to review studies on the link between gender equality and productivity, and they found that the evidence for a causal correlation is weak. This led the change agents to stress the ethical aspects of equality more strongly in communicating the project, which was appreciated by employees. The BAF project from the start both expected to see and noted resistance from the organisation.

- **The ethical dimension**

The FGF project aimed to improve both organisational goals and gender equality; in Sweden, it is deemed politically incorrect to oppose gender equality, which means people may try to hide or redirect their objections to change in such initiatives – for instance by disguising or redirecting resistance into other forms of opposition. To address this issue, change agents should try to uncover and make visible any resistance to gender equality initiatives.

Fair treatment and organisational justice can create a positive attitude towards change and fairness can also be seen as a competitive advantage; a sense of fair play and solidarity are positive qualities that can facilitate efforts to change gender relations. Change efforts aiming at gender equality may be more easily accepted in workplaces where employees have strong feelings of

justice. To overcome resistance to change in gender relations, it may be useful to stress the aspects of fair play in the proposed change without silencing opposition.

Results and Discussion

Here, in the Results and Discussion section, the lessons learnt from the presented case studies of FGF and BAF will be compared to the RES4CITY project and its gender diversity work. It is however important to keep in mind the different natures of WiTEC's involvement in RES4CITY, compared to the action research projects FGF and BAF – therefore, analogies are at risk of being misleading if too directly applied. Instead, as advised in the Introduction, it was worth considering RES4CITY as a large system consisting of many groups intersecting in either the development or utilisation of the project's interventions. In the following discussion, we will therefore analyze the system at these different levels.

As we learned from studying the FGF and BAF projects, the initiation of a project plays a significant role in its potential for success.

Whether the project is started by external researchers or initiated internally within the organisation, the way it is initiated can have a profound impact on its legitimacy and acceptance. In the case of RES4CITY, gender diversity is already included on the agenda; in this internal initiation there is a greater chance of success as the objectives are more likely to be seen as aligned with the organisation's goals, values, and culture.

Voluntariness plays a crucial role in the success in the adoption of perspectives and frameworks, and it can take different forms. In the RES4CITY project, a gender diversity aspect was stipulated to be a part of the project from the beginning – from this perspective, it can be argued that this inclusion was not necessarily voluntarily driven but rather a mandatory requirement; from another perspective, the rate of voluntariness would rather be made visible in whether the interest in and practical

applications of gender diversity measures, for instance as proposed in the Gender Equality Plan (GEP). In the practical interventions of the RES4CITY project, such as the educational frameworks and industry-academia partnerships, the issue of voluntariness is once again relevant; here, it is key to consider how gender diversity aspects might be perceived by external collaborators in partnerships, and eventually students and participants – to engage the collaborators in a transparent discourse might be a way to avoid triggering resistance.

As documented in the FGF project, RES4CITY has similar epistemological conditions given the project's ties to academic and educational subjects; as we learned in the comparative case study, this means better conditions for familiarisation with theoretical concepts and knowledge about gender diversity perspectives – and eventually also better implementations

of the GEP in RES4CITY's different steps of the project.

Regarding the topic of equality, we consider the co-operating internal bodies within the RES4CITY project to be at similar. On the other hand, it is important to be aware of interactions with external partners during the project – by assuring that the potential status gaps are bridged, a more transparent exchange of ideas and feedback can be attained, which for instance could be key in obtaining information about how specific targeted interventions may have affected the targeted group. On a similar note, the question of powering the core group is here important; core groups can for instance be thought of as being female and marginalised student groups – whose conditions are in focus in the work of WiTEC – and academic and industry partners with special experience and knowledge of these student group's patterns in their local society.

Conclusion and Recommendations

To conclude the findings in this case study, some success factors in change initiatives have been found:

- 1) Internal initiation** – change projects initiated from within the organisation, involving employees and key stakeholders, tend to have higher legitimacy and acceptance.
- 2) Voluntary participation** – involving individuals who have a genuine interest in the project and are willing to contribute voluntarily increases commitment and enthusiasm.
- 3) Integration of theory and practice** – providing clear and intelligible explanations of theoretical frameworks and linking them to practical implementation helps in garnering support and understanding within the organisation.

4) Adequate expertise and knowledge – having individuals with the necessary expertise and knowledge, such as researchers or professionals familiar with the subject matter, helps in integrating relevant research and effectively addressing the identified issues.

5) Time for research and change process – recognising that research and change take time and avoiding the expectation of quick fixes enables a more thorough and comprehensive approach to achieving the desired outcomes.

6) Bridging status gaps – ensuring equality and raising the status of participating employees can foster better collaboration and engagement in the change process.

7) Alliance with committed collaborators – establishing alliances with individuals or groups who share the

commitment to change increases the likelihood of successful collaboration and implementation.

8) Evolutionary approach – implementing changes that are seen as evolutionary rather than revolutionary can help mitigate resistance, especially when challenging the status quo or addressing ingrained gender relations.

9) Addressing resistance – being sensitive to employee reactions and interpreting them as potential areas of resistance helps in understanding concerns and addressing them effectively.

10) Fairness and justice – emphasizing fairness and organisational justice in the change process creates a positive attitude towards change and can be seen as a competitive advantage.

These points therefore lay as foundation for the recommendations of this case study and may be used as a guideline for change initiatives within an organisation.

References

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